

ADVANTAGES OF ONLINE EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Online education has become increasingly popular due to its flexibility and accessibility. This paper examines the advantages and disadvantages of online education. The advantages of online education include flexibility in scheduling, accessibility for students in remote areas, and the ability to study at one's own pace.

Key words: advantage, distance e-learning, flexible, online learning

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Introduction

Online education, also known as distance learning, has become increasingly popular in recent years. With the advancement of technology, students now have the opportunity to access quality education from the comfort of their own homes. Lynch (1999) said that online learning contents educational experience materials. And it brings out effect for new age learners' life, the life of their teachers, their families, the community and the institution. This flexible mode of learning offers a variety of advantages, but it also comes with some disadvantages that should be considered. We can say that despite the problems such as poor communication and internet traffic, it has advantages. And there are some advantage of online education:

Advantages to online education, including flexibility in scheduling, accessibility from anywhere with an internet connection, a wide range of course options, and often lower costs compared to traditional in-person education. Additionally, online education can cater to different learning styles and allow for self-paced learning. Now we get to know closely:

First one is Flexibility: Online education allows students to access course materials and lectures at any time and from anywhere, making it easier to balance their studies with other responsibilities such as work or family. Also, this form of education goes well work. As a rule, the time of online study can be easily adjusted to almost any work schedule (Menas et.al., 2009).

Second one is Accessibility: With online education, students have the opportunity to access courses and educational resources that may not be available in their local area, opening up opportunities for learning that were previously inaccessible.

Third one is Cost-effective: Online education often costs less than traditional in-person education, as it eliminates the need for commuting, housing, and other expenses associated with attending a physical campus [1, 57-61].

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HUMANISTIC ROLE OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE CONTEMPORARY GLOBALIZATION

Online learning is a form of distance learning or distance education, which has long been a part of the American education system, and it has become the largest sector of distance learning in recent years (Bartley & Golek, 2004, Evans & Haase, 2001 [2, 167-175]. [3,246-260].

Agarwal and Pandey (2013) explain that e-learning become the method of training teacher in educational field, here are some benefits eLearning when it compared with traditional methods: e-learning is cheaper that traditional methods of teaching because it doesn't need paper or pencil and it can be do in any place and any time; e-learning is more flexible environment for students; and personalization means that in e-learning the training material is not chosen by teacher or some organization and can help students to obtain their own requirement of knowledge.

You are free to get an education at any university in the work (Ahem and Repman,1994). This availability is the main advantage of distance learning. And also, we know that not only middle-aged people but even young children go to different educational centers and live in certain houses far away from their parents, which creates homesickness and social isolation causes it to fail. We know that education centers teach from 2 hours to 4 hours and you have the opportunity to get materials, for example, training exercises or study guide, only by going to the teacher's class, can easily learn with 24 hours without spending any energy. We can get study guides. Furthermore, the ability to learn at your own pace.

Lastly, another advantage of online education is the ability to learn at your own pace. Every student has their own pace of studying, and this is where the advantages of distance learning really come into play.

Online classes give you the ability to set your own pace, review material as needed and move through the coursework in a way that suits your learning style.

Learning at your own pace lets you have ultimate control over your learning process, so it really is one of the biggest benefits of online classes.

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